

A Hybrid Type 2 Effectiveness-Implementation Evaluation of HIV-1/HIV-2 Differential Testing
and Risk Compensation among Lenacapavir PrEP Users in Kenya

By

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Abstract

Background: In February 2026, Kenya initiated a phased rollout of twice-yearly injectable Lenacapavir (LEN) for HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) across 15 high-priority counties. However, LEN exhibits a critical pharmacological constraint, demonstrating an 11- to 25-fold reduction in potency against HIV-2 compared to HIV-1. In this low-prevalence landscape, standard clinical routines frequently fail to record specific HIV-2 results from primary discriminatory assays, a gap potentially exacerbated by PrEP-associated risk compensation across sexual and injection practices.

Objectives: The primary objective is to evaluate the dual impact of integrating routine HIV-1/2 differential testing on clinical effectiveness and implementation success, while assessing the influence of risk compensation among Lenacapavir PrEP users in Kenya. Briefly, the specific objectives are to: (1) determine the incidence and yield of HIV-1 and HIV-2 detections in a longitudinal cohort; (2) evaluate implementation outcomes (feasibility, adoption, and reach) at 3-month visits using the RE-AIM framework; (3) assess risk compensation by measuring longitudinal changes in high-risk practices from initiation to 3-month follow-up ; and (4) identify barriers and facilitators influencing testing integration, specifically provider failure to differentiate strains using the TrinScreen.

Methodology: This study employs a hybrid Type 2 effectiveness-implementation design utilizing a convergent parallel mixed-methods approach. A longitudinal cohort of HIV-negative adults (N = 300) initiating LEN PrEP will be purposively sampled across high-burden clinics in Nairobi, Homabay, and Kisumu. Quantitative data collection will occur at baseline (0 months) and follow-up (3 months) via TrinScreen screening and behavioral surveys, complemented by qualitative semi-structured interviews (n =20 - 40) with clients and providers. Quantitative data will be analyzed using logistic regression to evaluate behavioral predictors of seroconversion, while qualitative data will undergo thematic analysis.

Significance: By evaluating the diagnostic accuracy and Positive Predictive Value (PPV) of the TrinScreen's discriminatory lines in a low-prevalence environment, this research mitigates the risk of diagnostic misclassification, preserving future therapeutic pathways for drug-resistant strains. Furthermore, by quantifying compensatory behavioral shifts, this study provides critical empirical evidence to the National Syndemic Diseases Control Council (NSDCC) and the Ministry of Health. These findings will directly inform national clinical guidelines and guide the scalable integration of differential testing within long-acting PrEP rollout infrastructures globally.

Keywords: Lenacapavir; HIV-2 Surveillance; Hybrid Type 2 Design; Risk Compensation; TrinScreen; Implementation Science; Kenya.

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1.0 Introduction

Statistics indicate that since the recorded first HIV infection, about 91.4 million have been infected with HIV and about 44.1 million have died from HIV-related causes. Furthermore, about 40.8 million were recorded to have been living with HIV at the end of 2024. Out of this, it was estimated that 0.7% of adult aged 15-49 years globally live with HIV. The same report showed that African region is overburdened with almost 1 in every 30 adults infected with. This accounts for all HIV infections worldwide minus one-thirds (Carter et al., 2024; *HIV and AIDS Epidemic Global Statistics*, 2024; UNAIDS, 2024; UNICEF, 2024; WHO, 2024). In 2024, HIV prevalence in Kenya was recorded at 3.0%, with females at (4.0%) and males at (2.0 %). That same year, it was estimated that 1,326,336 people were living with HIV. Among this, 62,798 were children and 132,018 were young adults aged 15–24 years. Although the new HIV infections declined by 51.7 percent, from 41,416 in 2019 to 19,991 in 2024, efforts are underway to reduce it further (NSDCC, 2025.). These efforts have led to a transformative change in the global HIV prevention setting, with the introduction of long-acting injectable pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) known as Lenacapavir (LEN). Lenacapavir operates by inhibiting viral capsid and is given out twice yearly. This drug denotes a breakthrough in biomedical prevention, presenting superior efficacy and enhanced adherence over daily oral regimens. In February 2026, Kenya became the first East African country to launch a phased rollout of LEN PrEP, aiming at 21,000 initial doses across 15 HIV priority counties.

However, the clinical success of this rollout is dependent upon diagnostic precision. Lenacapavir exhibits a substantial pharmacological drawback, as it is 11 to 25 times less potent against HIV-2 than HIV-1. In the Kenyan context, where HIV-2 prevalence is almost negligible, the emergence of drug-resistant discoveries, compounded by potential risk compensation involving condomless sex and the sharing of unsterilized needles and syringes, presents a unique public health challenge. This research employs a Hybrid Type 2 implementation-effectiveness design to evaluate the incorporation of routine differential HIV-1/HIV-2 testing (TrinScreen) within the national PrEP framework. Through that the research addresses the critical gap between available diagnostic technology and actual clinical practice.

1.1 Background and Rationale

Annals depict Kenya as one of the most vigorous HIV responses in the Sub-Saharan region, with an adult prevalence at nearly 4.3% according to recent estimates, and ongoing declines in new infections due to prolonged antiretroviral therapy (ART), and prevention efforts. The February 2026 national inauguration of Lenacapavir (LEN) as a prolonged injectable pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP)—administered twice yearly—marks a revolutionary step. Kenya is the first East African country to introduce LEN PrEP by initiating rollout of 21,000 initial doses targeting 15 counties that are highly burdened, with phased national expansion planned. However, LEN reveals reduced potency against HIV-2 (that is 11 to 25 times less potent than HIV-1), creating a potential prevention hitch, if this strain is not monitored.

LEN offers substantial protection in trials and higher efficacy over daily oral PrEP in diverse populations. Yet, the high perceived security of an injectable could trigger risk compensation, where users significantly reduce protective behaviors recommended by medical experts across multiple transmission routes. This shift encompasses not only a reduction in consistent condom use but also the potential for increased sharing of unsterilized needles and syringes among key populations who perceive the long-acting injection as a total biological shield. Combined with LEN's lower activity against HIV-2, this behavioral change could puzzlingly increase the risk of acquiring this rare, drug-resistant strain. HIV-2 remains enormously infrequent in East Africa, including Kenya, where the epidemic is overwhelmingly HIV-1 driven. National surveillance, sentinel data, and population surveys report negligible or absent HIV-2 circulation, contrasting with higher prevalence in West Africa.

Kenya's standard HIV diagnostic procedures depend on serological rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) in a three-test serial stratagem, utilizing the TrinScreen as the primary assay. While the TrinScreen possesses discriminatory lines for HIV-1 and HIV-2, current clinical practice and reporting tools often do not mandate routine differentiation or specific recording of HIV-2 results unless clinically showed. In low-prevalence sceneries, undifferentiated or misclassified HIV-2 cases could theoretically go undetected particularly during PrEP instigation or breakthrough monitoring, possibly delaying ideal management. There remains a critical need to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy and Positive Predictive Value (PPV) of the TrinScreen's discriminatory

capacity within this 3-test framework to ensure breakthroughs are accurately identified and false positives are minimized.

This study addresses a critical surveillance blind spot: whether entrenching routine differential HIV-1/HIV-2 testing in LEN PrEP rollout is feasible, acceptable, and yields meaningful public health benefits. It aligns with implementation science priorities for long-acting PrEP scale-up, health equity in diagnostics, and evidence-informed guideline adaptation.

1.2 Problem Statement

Notwithstanding the clinical efficacy of Lenacapavir (LEN) demonstrated in Phase 2/3 trials, its rollout in Kenya triggers critical questions regarding diagnostic readiness in low-HIV-2 backgrounds. Current protocols primarily target HIV-1, potentially ignoring rare HIV-2 or dual infections, which endangers the accuracy of breakthrough responses and longitudinal surveillance. This risk is exacerbated by a documented 'condom quandary' among young gay and bisexual men in Nairobi, where the perceived total protection of injectable PrEP may lead to significant risk compensation, including reduced condom use and the potential sharing of unsterilized needles and syringes. Furthermore, laboratory evidence confirms that both HIV-1 and HIV-2 can develop specific mutations under Lenacapavir pressure, necessitating rigorous molecular and biological monitoring. Adding differential testing could augment diagnostic accuracy and protect the 2026 rollout, yet no empirical data currently exist on integrating biological and behavioral monitoring during a large-scale Lenacapavir implementation in East Africa (Cheruiyot et al., 2025).

2.0 Literature Review

Beneath is a thorough analysis of existing literature on topics related to this study on HIV prevention and Lenacapavir.

2.1 The Biological Vulnerability of HIV-1/2

While Lenacapavir (LEN) has demonstrated 96% to 100% efficacy against HIV-1 the first and second trials (Bekker et al., 2024; Kelley et al., 2025; Ogbuagu et al., 2023; Sah et al., 2025; Thornhill & Orkin, 2021; Tuan & Ogbuagu, 2023), its action against HIV-2 is considerably reduced. In vitro studies indicate that LEN is 11 to 25 times less potent against HIV-2 strain compared to HIV-1, with a half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values shifting from 200 pM (HIV-1) to 2.2 nM (HIV-2) (Smith et al., 2024), this is because of their distinct structural nature (Hui et al., 2025; Tao et al., 2024). Further clinical case studies have confirmed that in multidrug-resistant HIV-2 patients, LEN-containing regimens failed to achieve virological suppression after one year, often leading to the rapid emergence of the N73D capsid mutation, which further reduces drug susceptibility by 30 times (Smith et al., 2024; van Kampen et al., 2025). This is a critical gap because even low-nanomolar (concentration of drug required to inhibit the virus) activity may not prevent users with sub-optimal drug (too low concentration of medication in the blood or tissue) levels or high-risk exposure (Widera et al., 2017).

2.2 The Implementation Gap

Kenya's 2026 rollout of LEN across 15 high-priority counties relies on TrinScreen HIV-1/2 rapid diagnostic test (RDT) for screening (*NASCOP HIV Testing Algorithm*, 2022). The TrinScreen is designed to differentiate between the two strains of HIV, but clinical routine tests often neglect the discriminatory line, and clinicians do not state which strain the patient is diagnosed with. Without this critical information, HIV-2 breakthroughs which are naturally resistant to ARVs, remain undiagnosed. This further risk the rapid emergence of capsid-inhibitor resistance which may lead to surging number of HIV-2 infections in the future and related-health outcomes.

2.3 Behavioral Risk Compensation

The transition to a bi-annual injectable LEN may trigger risk compensation, where users perceive a total shield against HIV and subsequently reduce other preventive behaviors. In Kenya, where HIV prevalence remains high in counties like Nairobi (15.19%) and Kisumu (10.96%) (NSDCC, 2025), any shift toward suboptimal preventive behaviors, specifically the simultaneous reduction in condom usage and the sharing of unsterilized needles, could paradoxically increase exposure to the very strains LEN is least equipped to handle. Recent qualitative evidence from Nairobi confirms this ‘condom quandary,’ as young men initiating PrEP report that perceived high efficacy of the medication leads them to question the added value barrier methods. Furthermore, significant barriers such as PrEP-related stigma and fear of being perceived as living with HIV continue to drive users towards discrete injectable options, potentially masking these behavioral shifts from routine clinical oversight.

2.4 Research Gap

- Limited real-world data exists on HIV-2 breakthrough rates among Lenacapavir (LEN) users, particularly given the drug's 11- to 25-fold reduced potency against this specific strain compared to HIV-1.
- There is a significant absence of empirical evidence regarding how risk compensation—extending beyond reduced condom use to include the potential sharing of unsterilized injecting equipment—influences exposure to rare HIV-2 variants following the initiation of long-acting injectables.
- Evidence is currently lacking on the diagnostic accuracy and Positive Predictive Value (PPV) of the TrinScreen's discriminatory lines when deployed within Kenya's "near-zero" HIV-2 prevalence environment.
- While the TrinScreen has been adopted as the primary assay in the national 3-test algorithm, a critical gap exists where healthcare providers frequently fail to identify or differentiate the specific HIV-1/HIV-2 discriminatory lines, leaving them unrecorded in standard reporting tools.

- Hybrid designs remain underutilized for evaluating the operational feasibility of mandating and recording routine differential results to monitor LEN breakthroughs within existing East African clinical workflows.

3.0 Objectives

Primary Objective

To evaluate the dual impact of integrating routine HIV-1/2 differential testing on clinical effectiveness and implementation success, while assessing the influence of risk compensation among Lenacapavir PrEP users in Kenya.

3.1 Specific Objectives

1. To determine the incidence and yield of HIV-1 and HIV-2 detections using differential testing in a longitudinal cohort of Lenacapavir PrEP users.
2. To evaluate implementation outcomes, specifically feasibility, adoption, and reach, of integrating differential testing into routine 3-month PrEP injection visits using the RE-AIM framework.
3. To assess the extent of risk compensation by measuring longitudinal changes in high-risk practices, specifically the sharing of unsterilized needles and syringes and condomless sex, from PrEP initiation to the 3-month follow-up.
4. To identify the barriers and facilitators influencing the integration of differential testing, specifically the failure of providers to identify and differentiate HIV-1 from HIV-2 despite the availability of discriminatory kits (TrinScreen).

3.2 Research Questions

1: What is the incidence of HIV-1 and HIV-2 infections among Lenacapavir PrEP users, and how accurately does the TrinScreen differentiate these breakthroughs in a real-world Kenyan clinical setting?

2: What is the Positive Predictive Value (PPV) of the TrinScreen's HIV-2 discriminatory line when applied within the national 3-test algorithm in a low-prevalence environment?

3: How does the initiation of Lenacapavir influence risk compensation, specifically regarding the transition toward higher-risk practices such as the sharing of unsterilized needles and injecting equipment?

4: What are the primary systemic and provider-level barriers that lead to the HIV-2 discriminatory line on the TrinScreen being ignored or unrecorded during routine PrEP follow-up visits?

4.0 Methodologies

4.1 Study Design

This dissertation employs a hybrid Type 2 effectiveness-implementation design (Curran et al., 2012) to evaluate the integration of routine differential HIV-1/2 testing within the 2026 Lenacapavir rollout. The study utilizes a convergent parallel mixed-methods approach to assess both the clinical prevention of specific strains and the implementation context via the RE-AIM framework. A longitudinal cohort study (N=300) monitoring HIV-negative individuals initiating Lenacapavir. The focus is on identifying breakthrough infections at 3 months and categorizing them by strain to evaluate Lenacapavir's real-world effectiveness against HIV-2 in the context of risk compensation. Semi-structured interviews (n =20–40) with providers and clients to explore the acceptability of the differential testing protocol and the perceived invincibility of injectable PrEP.

4.2 Study Population

The study population consists of HIV-negative adults (N=300) eligible for Lenacapavir (LEN) PrEP according to Kenyan national guidelines. Participants will be purposively sampled from initiation and follow-up clinics across three high-burden counties: Nairobi, Homabay, and Kisumu. Inclusion criteria require individuals to be at high risk of infection, including those reporting condomless sex or the use of unsterilized needles/syringes, ensuring the sample reflects populations most vulnerable to the LEN prevention drawback regarding HIV-2.

4.3 Sample Size Determination

In this study, the Cochran's Formula was used to calculate the sample size. This was done purposely to calculate the minimum number of participants required to detect a specific proportion of HIV-2 breakthrough with statistical confidence. The Formula, $n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p(1-p)}{e^2}$

Where;

Confidence (Z): At 95% confidence level, Z is 1.96.

Estimated proportion (p): Is the estimated incidence of the event. For rare events of HIV-2 breakthroughs in a low-prevalence setting, the study utilizes a conservative estimate of 5% (p =

0.05). This value is utilized as a conservative variance because the actual clinical breakthrough rate of HIV-2 in Kenya's low-prevalence setting is expected to be near-zero.

Margin of Error (e): The study will use a precision level of 2.5% (e = 0.025) to ensure we do not miss these rare cases.

It should be noted that utilizing p = 0.05 with a highly rigorous precision level (e = 0.025) ensures the study achieves the maximum possible statistical power to detect rare diagnostic anomalies within the cohort framework.

Calculation: $n = \frac{1.96^2 \cdot 0.05 \cdot (0.95)}{0.025^2} \approx 292 \text{ participants}$

The study picked 300 participants by rounding up the sample size to obtain enough statistical power to identify if the TrinScreen yield is higher than standard tests. It was also rounded up for attrition buffer as longitudinal studies in high-risk populations often face a 20% to 25% drop-out rate over longer periods, the study's compressed 3-month follow-up window significantly mitigates the risk of many drop-outs.

4.4 Sampling Method

This study uses purposive sampling combined with snowball sampling because it targets a specific high-risk group (Lenacapavir users with suboptimal behavioral prevention strategies like needle sharing and condomless sex).

4.5 Data Collection

Data collection will be conducted by dedicated clinicians during two accelerated recruitment phases (April and July 2027): Firstly, quantitative data will be collected at baseline (0 month), where all potential participants are screened with the TrinScreen RDT; those testing positive for either strain will be excluded and referred for ART. For the enrolled (N=300), data on baseline risk behaviors (needle-sharing and condom use) are recorded. Secondly, after 3 months, repeat differential testing will be performed. If seroconversion occurs, the specific strain (HIV-1 or HIV-2) is recorded as a primary outcome.

Furthermore, qualitative data will be collected through semi-structured interviews to help understand the implementation experience. These sessions will be audio-recorded to ensure an accurate, verbatim account of participant attitudes toward risk compensation and the necessity of strain-specific results.

4.6 Analysis

Quantitative data will be analyzed in R or STATA. The incidence of HIV-1 compared to HIV-2 breakthroughs will be calculated. Logistic regression will be used to determine if self-reported high-risk practices (recorded via surveys) are statistically significant predictors of HIV-2 seroconversion.

Furthermore, qualitative data from recorded interviews will be transcribed and thematically analyzed using NVivo. This analysis will explain the human factors—such as why a participant felt they no longer needed sterile needles after their Lenacapavir injection.

Finally, quantitative results (the number of HIV-2 breakthroughs) will be merged with qualitative insights (perceptions of LEN's total protection) to provide a holistic evaluation of the 2026 rollout.

4.7 Ethics

Ethical approval will be sought from the University of Bristol Faculty of Health Sciences Research Ethics Committee and Kenyan authorities, for example, NACOSTI if required. Procedures will ensure informed consent, confidentiality, minimal risk, and compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Kenya Data Protection Act (2019).

5.0 Significance of the Study

The findings of this research will have a direct impact on the clinical, policy, and behavioral frameworks of Kenya's 2026 Lenacapavir (LEN) rollout through the following contributions:

- By recognizing the specific barriers preventing healthcare providers from differentiating HIV-1 and HIV-2 on the TrinScreen, this study will offer the evidence needed to inform national nursing guidelines. This ensures that the identifying the strain step is no longer

ignored, protecting patients from mismanaged, drug-resistant breakthroughs and efficacy of LEN in preventing HIV-1 solidified, while its inability to protect humans from HIV-2 infection affirmed.

- The evaluation of the Positive Predictive Value (PPV) in a near-zero prevalence environment will determine the reliability of current rapid tests for LEN users. This prevents unnecessary patient anxiety caused by false positives while ensuring that true HIV-2 infections are caught early, preserving future treatment options.
- By quantifying risk compensation, this research will inform the National Syndemic Diseases Control Council (NSDCC) on how LEN initiation influences a broad spectrum of increased risk-taking behaviors—specifically the simultaneous reduction in condom usage and the increased sharing of unsterilized needles and syringes. This ensures that LEN is not rolled out in a vacuum but is integrated with comprehensive sexual health and needle-exchange programs.
- Utilizing a Hybrid Type 2 design allows this study to offer insights that inform policies in Kenya and Worldwide. The results will guide the Ministry of Health on the operational feasibility of mandating differential testing nationwide, ensuring that the 21,000-dose initial rollout is buoyed by a robust and accurate diagnostic infrastructure.

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